

**Notes—Forthcoming Energy and Climate Law
Quarterly—2021**

NON-STATE ACTORS AND CLIMATE LITIGATION: THE
SUPREME COURT OF IRELAND STRIKES DOWN CLIMATE
POLICY APPROVED BY THE IRISH GOVERNMENT

[Supreme Court of Ireland, 31st July 2020, Appeal
No: 205/19]

The contribution of the case is very significant. It underlines that climate change is one of the greatest concerns facing mankind. As a result, climate change issues must be addressed, and predominantly by governments, because states are in the first instance responsible of environment protection on their territory. Hence, it seems no longer enough for states to tackle climate change anyhow, including designing climate policies that are far from the realities on the ground, scientific realm or failing to vindicate the rights guaranteed by pertinent legal instruments.

The leave to appeal sought by the Friends of the Irish Environment (FIE) is in line with this approach. The facts, as acquired at trial, can thus be summarized as follows: pursuant to the article 3 of the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development Act, 2015, the Government of Ireland published on the 19th July 2017, the National Mitigation Plan. The object of the plan was to provide a climate action policy framework for initiating and pursuing the transition to a low carbon, climate resilient and environmentally sustainable economy. First, the plan pointed out that the Irish climate action aimed at contributing to the global response to the climate challenge, which rely on the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement. In this regard, the plan pledges to pursue the objectives of restricting global temperature rise, and endeavor the collective effort to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C. Then, the plan referred to the

European Union (EU) action as to the objectives of reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and the contribution of the Republic of Ireland to the EU effort, supporting at the same the Irish approach of fostering climate resilience and low greenhouse gas emissions development.

In this context, FIE, an environmental non-governmental organisation, which operates actively in the area of protection and the promotion of the Irish environment, instituted proceedings before Mr. Justice MacGrath. First, because it fails to approve acceptable means to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in compliance with the objectives of the UNFCCC, the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement, the applicant contends that the Plan is unconstitutional. Accordingly, the Plan will violate the rights of the applicant, the rights of its members and the general public, namely the rights enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights and Freedoms. Second, FIE argues that the plan was adopted in breach of the European Convention on Fundamental Rights. Finally, the applicant claims that the plan is *ultra vires* the powers of the Minister under the Act. In order to sustain its contention, the applicant alleges that the decision of the Irish Government to approve the Plan should be abrogated, because it does not comply with the section 4 of the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development Act, 2015. It is also argued that the Plan does not contain any appropriate measures susceptible 'to achieve the management of a reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in order to attain emission levels appropriate for furthering the achievement of the National Transition Objective.'

FIE raised the issue that the government plan will fail to achieve the desired objectives and the necessary steps for a better evaluation of the government action on mitigating concentrations throughout the period during which the reduction of emissions is made and supported. It is the responsibility of the government to prevent the irreversible damage that might occur from maintaining the current level of GHG emissions in the atmosphere. FIE stresses the necessity of reducing

the emissions in a steep direction and in line with the projection need in order to support international regulation relating to climate issues. It is argued that despite the effort of combating climate change, the current trajectory of emissions and the level of concentration will still alter the atmosphere. As regards Government Plan, its objective of achieving a reduction by 2050 is sustained by mechanisms that do not prevent the risk of harm inherent to the short-term incautious reduction of emissions.

The civil society organisation broadly emphasises that scientific evidence now suggests that net negative carbon dioxide emissions must be maintained within 2°C. In this sense, it appears indispensable that political efforts must be made in favour of scenarios that allow the development of carbon dioxide removal technologies such as bioenergy, extensive reforestation and forest growth will be necessary. Accordingly, FIE raises the point that the mitigation plan must be based on concrete calculations that can define a new trajectory of emission reductions in the short term in a serious and substantial way. To support this, it is argued that the government's focus on long-term targets will simply affect carbon budgets. In this regard, FIE contends that by developing and approving the plan, the government is not doing enough to combat climate change; as a result, the plan is approved in a violation of the law and of the plaintiff's rights, which it is for the courts to review and uphold.

After considering the arguments and conclusions reached by the parties, the judge held that, in light of the discretion exercised by the government in developing and adopting the Plan under the Act, it could not be decided that the government had violated the provisions of the Act in the manner alleged. Accordingly, it is concluded that the Plan refers to the State's obligations under European Union law and existing international agreements. In this respect, it could not be considered to contain any proposal to achieve the national objective of transition which, as provided for in Article 3(1), leads to the completion of the transition by

2050. Moreover, the judge noted that the Plan does indeed specify the policy measures that the government considers necessary to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Those reasons led the High Court to dismiss the FIE proceedings. From then on, FIE sought leave to appeal to the Court.

FIE was granted leave to appeal by decision of 13 February 2020. This leave was substantial by the fact that there was a common understanding in the arguments of both plaintiff and defendant on the need for urgent action to combat climate change. In this sense, it appears that the parties do not dispute the importance of understanding and putting in place the means to combat climate change, in particular with regard to the likely increase in greenhouse gas emissions during the duration of the plan. In this regard, the authorisation was granted on the basis of the Parties' common understanding of the seriousness of the likely effects of climate change.

In this case, the judge came to some interesting conclusions.

Firstly, the decision rules on the standing of FIE. As it is a legal person not enjoying in itself the right to life or the right to bodily integrity, the decision concludes that it does not have standing in respect of the rights it seeks to assert under the Constitution or the ECHR. In support of this, the decision finds that it is not necessary to grant FIE standing under the exception to the general rule.

Second, the decision highlights numerous considerations with respect to the merits of the case. At the outset, it is stressed that FIE should be allowed to make a broad range of arguments in support of its written submissions. Similarly, the justiciable nature of the issues raised does not allow for a finding of inadmissible encroachment by the courts into areas of policy, as the policy aspects of this issue are now framed by the 2015 Act.

It is also held that the 2015 Law, by virtue of its Article 4, provides for a sufficient level of specificity in the measures identified in the plan with a view to achieving the national transition objective by 2050, which alone makes it possible to make a reasonable

assessment of the realistic nature of the plan and the policy options it contains. The decision therefore recalls that the adoption of the 2015 law has led to the use of certain mechanisms such as public participation in the process leading to the adoption of the plans and transparency regarding the government's official policy on the national transition objective. In this regard, it is noted that the plan advocated by the government must be sufficiently precise, even if it is not certain that the details of the evolution of the climate situation are known. To this extent, the plan must define the policy to be followed over the entire period up to 2050. Consequently, it would not be sufficient to set up a five-year plan.

In view of these considerations, the decision concludes that the plan should be quashed, as it "[...] falls far short of the level of specificity required to ensure such transparency and to comply with the provisions of the 2015 Law." The decision strongly emphasizes that a plan of such a nature cannot be sustained in the future.